

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of lower oxyacids of phosphorous by morpholinium chlorochromate

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Manuscript received 28 March 2007, accepted 27 June 2007

Abstract : Oxidation of lower oxyacids of phosphorous by morpholinium chlorochromate (MCC) in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) leads to the formation of corresponding oxyacids with phosphorous in a higher oxidation state. The reaction exhibits 1 : 1 stoichiometry. The reaction is first order with respect to MCC and the oxyacids. The reaction does not induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. Reactions are catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of deuteriated phosphinic (DPA) and phosphorous acids (DPPA) exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect. The oxidation was studied in nineteen different organic solvents. The solvent effects were analysed in terms of Taft's and Swain's multiparametric equations. The effect of solvent indicates the solvent polarity plays a major role in the process. It has been shown that the pentacoordinated tautomer of the phosphorous oxyacid is the reactive reductant and it has been concluded that tricoordinated forms of phosphorous oxyacids does not participate in the oxidation process. A mechanism involving transfer of a hydride ion in the rate-determining step has been proposed.

Keywords : Lower oxyacids, phosphorous, morpholinium chlorochromate.

Halochromates have been used as mild and selective oxidizing reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹⁻⁵. Morpholinium chlorochromate (MCC) is also one of such compounds used for the oxidation of primary aliphatic alcohols⁶. We have been interested in the kinetic and mechanistic studies of the reactions of chromium(VI) species and have already reported the mechanistic studies by several halochromates viz. pyridinium and quinolinium halochromates⁷⁻¹⁰. The lower oxyacids are reported to exist in two tautomeric forms^{11,12}, and it is of interest to determine the nature of the oxyacid involved in the oxidation process. There seems to be no report on the oxidation of oxyacids of phosphorous by MCC. Therefore, we report here the kinetics of oxidation of phosphinic (PA), phenylphosphinic (PPA) and phosphorous (POA) acids by MCC in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) as a solvent. A suitable mechanism has also been proposed.

Experimental

Materials : The phosphorous oxyacids were commercial products (Fluka) and were used as supplied. MCC was prepared by the reported method⁶, its purity was checked by an iodometric method and melting point de-

termination. Deuteriated phosphinic (DPA) and phosphorous acids (DPOA) were prepared by repeatedly dissolving the acid in deuterium oxide (BARC, 99.4%) and evaporating water and the excess of deuterium oxide *in vacuo*¹³. The isotopic purity of the deuterated PA and POA, as determined from their NMR spectra, was $93 \pm 5\%$ and $94 \pm 5\%$ respectively. Due to the non-aqueous nature of the medium, toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. TsOH is a strong acid and in non-polar solvents like DMSO it is likely to be completely ionised. Other solvents were purified by their usual methods¹⁴.

Stoichiometry : The oxidation of lower oxyacids of phosphorous leads to the formation of corresponding oxyacids containing phosphorous in a higher oxidation state. Reaction mixtures were prepared containing a known excess of phosphinic or phosphorous acids. On completion of the reaction, the amount of phosphorous formed in the oxidation of phosphinic acid and the residual reductant in the oxidation of phosphorous acids were determined by reported method¹⁵. To determine the stoichiometry of the oxidation of PPA, a known excess of MCC was treated

with PPA and the residual MCC was determined spectrophotometrically at 365 nm after the completion of the reaction. The oxidation state of chromium in the completely reduced reaction mixture, determined by iodometric titration, was 3.90 ± 0.15 . The oxidation exhibited 1 : 1 stoichiometry and the overall reaction may therefore, be written as :

MCC undergoes two-electron change. This is in accordance with the earlier observations with PBC¹⁶, PCC¹⁷ and BTEACC¹⁸. It has already been shown that both PFC¹⁶ and PCC¹⁷ act as two electron oxidants and

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of oxyacids of phosphorous by MCC at 288 K

$10^3[\text{MCC}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Oxyacid] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}/(\text{s}^{-1})$		
		PA	PPA	POA
1.00	0.10	4.39	12.8	1.35
1.00	0.20	8.80	27.2	2.75
1.00	0.40	17.1	53.1	5.42
1.00	0.60	26.5	81.9	8.19
1.00	0.80	35.1	110	11.0
1.00	1.00	44.1	135	13.7
2.00	0.40	17.5	54.3	5.75
4.00	0.40	16.4	53.0	4.95
6.00	0.40	17.0	54.5	5.15
8.00	0.40	16.2	53.8	5.67
1.00	0.20	8.55 ^a	27.7 ^a	2.89 ^a

^aContained 0.005 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

are reduced to chromium(IV) species by determining the oxidation state of chromium by magnetic susceptibility, ESR and IR studies.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping an excess

($\times 15$ or greater) of the [oxyacid] over [MCC]. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were studied at constant temperature (± 0.1 K) and were followed by monitoring the decrease in the [MCC] spectrophotometrically at 365 nm for up to 80% reaction. Pseudo-first-order rate constants, k_{obs} , were evaluated from linear plots ($r > 0.990$) of $\log [\text{MCC}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rates were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constants, k_2 were determined from the relation : $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{oxyacid}]$.

Results

Rate laws : The reactions were found to be first order in MCC. The individual kinetic runs were strictly first order in MCC. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constant does not depend on the initial [MCC]. The reaction rate increases linearly with an increase in the [oxyacids] (Table 1).

Induced polymerization test : The oxidation of oxyacids, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on reaction rate (Table 1).

Table 2. Effect of hydrogen ion concentration on the oxidation of PPA by MCC

[MCC] = 0.001 mol dm ⁻³ ; [PPA] = 0.10 mol dm ⁻³ ; Temp. = 288 K	[H ⁺]					
	0.10	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}/\text{s}^{-1}$	14.5	17.1	22.0	25.2	30.6	36.0

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain importance of the cleavage of the P-H bond in the rate-determining step, oxidation of deuteriated PA and POA was studied. Results showed the presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (Table 3).

Effect of acidity : The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions (Table 2). The hydrogen-ion dependence has the following form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$. The values of a and

Table 3. Rate constants and activation parameters of oxidation of phosphorous oxyacids by MCC

Acid	$10^3 k_2/(\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1})$				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
PA	4.41	8.64	16.2	31.5	47.1 \pm 0.7	-127 \pm 2	84.8 \pm 0.5
PPA	13.5	23.4	38.7	65.7	37.4 \pm 0.5	-151 \pm 1	82.3 \pm 0.4
POA	1.37	2.61	4.86	9.18	45.6 \pm 0.6	-142 \pm 2	87.7 \pm 0.5
DPA	0.75	1.53	2.97	6.10	50.4 \pm 0.9	-130 \pm 3	89.1 \pm 0.7
DPOA	0.25	0.49	0.93	1.80	47.6 \pm 0.8	-149 \pm 2	91.9 \pm 0.7
$k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$	5.88	5.65	5.45	5.16 (PA)			
$k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$	5.48	5.32	5.22	5.10 (POA)			

b , for PPA, are $12.2 \pm 0.48 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $23.2 \pm 0.79 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively ($r = 0.9976$).

Effect of solvents : The oxidation of PPA was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited due to the solubility of MCC and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values k_2 at 298 K for the oxidation of PPA are recorded in Table 4.

Table 4. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of phenylphosphinic acid by MCC at 298 K

Solvents	$10^4 k_2$ (s^{-1})	Solvents	$10^4 k_2$ (s^{-1})
Chloroform	41.7	Acetic acid	2.29
1,2-Dichloroethane	63.1	Cyclohexane	0.93
Dichloromethane	51.3	Toluene	12.0
DMSO	234	Acetophenone	91.2
Acetone	58.9	THF	23.4
<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylformamide	97.7	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	13.5
Butanone	38.9	1,4-Dioxane	27.5
Nitrobenzene	67.6	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	10.7
Benzene	17.8	Carbon disulfide	5.25
Ethyl acetate	18.2		

Reactive oxidising species : The observed hydrogenation dependence suggests that the reaction follows the two mechanistic pathways, one is acid-independent and the other is acid dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of MCC to give a stronger oxidant and electrophile (2). Both MCC and MCCH^+ are reactive species with the protonated form being more reactive.

Formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar BTEACC¹⁹ and BPCC²⁰.

Discussion

Solvent effect : The rate constants of the oxidation, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS_2 was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (LESR) of Kamlet and Taft²¹ (3).

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (3)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α is the hydrogen

bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of eq. (3), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below as eqs. (4)–(7).

$$\log k_2 = -4.05 + 2.20 (\pm 0.32)\pi^* + 0.03 (\pm 0.26)\beta + 0.22 (\pm 0.25)\alpha \quad (4)$$

$$R^2 = 0.7928; \text{sd} = 0.29; n = 18; \psi = 0.50$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.00 + 2.12 (\pm 0.30)\pi^* + 0.10 (\pm 0.25)\beta \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 0.7816; \text{sd} = 0.29; n = 18; \psi = 0.49$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.02 + 2.51 (\pm 0.29)\pi^* \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.7790; \text{sd} = 0.28; n = 18; \psi = 0.48$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.76 + 0.49 (\pm 0.49)\beta \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0588; \text{sd} = 0.58; n = 18; \psi = 0.99$$

Here n is the number of data points and is the Exner's statistical parameter²².

Kamlet's²¹ triparametric equation explains ca. 79% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion²² the correlation is not even satisfactory (cf. eq. (3)). The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounted for ca. 78% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's²³ eq. (8) of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also.

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (8)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (8), separately with A and B and with $(A + B)$.

$$\log k_2 = 0.25 (\pm 0.03)A + 2.27 (\pm 0.03)B - 3.84 \quad (9)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9981; \text{sd} = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.05$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.07 (\pm 0.07)A - 2.60 \quad (10)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0005; \text{sd} = 0.60; n = 19; \psi = 0.97$$

$$\log k_2 = 2.25 (\pm 0.05)B - 3.91 \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9914; \text{sd} = 0.06; n = 19; \psi = 0.09$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.60 \pm 0.26(A+B) - 3.93 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.6928; \text{sd} = 0.33; n = 19; \psi = 0.57$$

The rates of oxidation of PPA in different solvents showed

an excellent correlation in Swain's equation (*cf.* eq. (11)) with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone account for *ca.* 99% of the data. The correlation with the anion-solvating power was very poor. The solvent polarity, represented by ($A + B$), also accounted for *ca.* 69% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 69% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.4848$; $sd = 0.43$; $\psi = 0.74$).

Reactive reducing species : Lower oxyacids of phosphorous are reported to exist in two tautomeric forms^{11,12}. The predominant species is the pentacoordinated form (A). The value²⁴ of the equilibrium constant, K_t , in aqueous solutions, is of the order of 10^{-12} .

Hence two alternative broad mechanisms can be formulated. Assuming in the first instance pentacoordinated tautomer (A) as the reactive reducing species, the following mechanism may be proposed which leads to the rate law (15).

$$\text{Rate} = k_a [\text{oxyacid}]_0 [\text{MCC}] / (1 + K_t) \quad (15)$$

where $[\text{oxyacid}]_0$ represents the initial concentration of the oxyacid. Eq. (15) can be reduced to (16) as $1 \gg K_t$.

$$\text{Rate} = k_a [\text{oxyacid}]_0 [\text{MCC}] \quad (16)$$

Another mechanism can be formulated assuming the tricoordinated form (B) as the reactive reducing species, eq. (17), which leads to the rate eq. (18).

$$\text{Rate} = k_b K_t [\text{oxyacid}]_0 [\text{MCC}] / (1 + K_t) \quad (18)$$

This rate law (18), can be reduced to (19), again acknowledging $1 \gg K_t$.

$$\text{Rate} = k_b K_t [\text{oxyacid}]_0 [\text{MCC}] \quad (19)$$

Thus the two rate equations confirm to the experimental rate-law and are kinetically indistinguishable.

If eqs. (13) and (17) represents the mechanism of the oxidation of oxyacids of phosphorous then the experimental specific rate-constant, $k_2 = K_t k_b$, the value of K_t is of the order of 10^{-12} . Therefore, the value of rate-limiting constant, k_b , ranges between 10^8 and 10^9 dm^3

$\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. This value exceeds/equals the rate constants of diffusion-controlled rate processes²⁵. Therefore, participation of tricoordinated form of the oxyacids in the oxidation processes can be ruled out.

Mechanism :

The absence of any effect of the radical scavenger on the reaction rate and the failure to induce polymerisation of acrylonitrile point against a one-electron oxidation giving rise to free radicals. The presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect confirms the cleavage of a P-H bond in the rate-determining step. A preferential cleavage of a P-H bond, in the rate-determining step, is likely in view of the relatively high bond dissociation energy of the O-H bond. The mean value of the bond dissociation energy of an O-H bond²⁶ is 460 kJ mol^{-1} , while that for a P-H bond²⁷ is 321 kJ mol^{-1} . Therefore, a hydride ion mechanism may be proposed for the oxidation of these oxyacids.

The proposed mechanism (Scheme 1) involving the hydride ion transfer in the rate determining step is also supported by the observed major role of cation-solvating power of the solvents.

Scheme 1

It is of interest to compare the mode of oxidation of lower oxyacids of phosphorous by PFC²⁸, PCC²⁹, PBC⁸ and MCC. The oxidation by PCC and MCC exhibited the second order kinetics, first with respect to each reactant. The oxidation by PFC exhibited a Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics. The rate-law, acid dependence, kinetic isotope effect are similar in both the cases. In all the three oxidations, excellent correlation were obtained in terms of Swain's equation with the cation solvating power of the solvents playing the major role.

The rate of oxidation follows the order : PPA > PA > POA. The faster rate of PPA could be explained on the basis of stabilisation of a positively polarized phosphorous, in the transition state, by the phenyl group through resonance. The slower rate of POA may well be due to the electron-withdrawing nature of hydroxyl group causing an electron-deficiency at the phosphorous atom. This makes the departure of an anion more difficult. A perusal of the activation parameters in Table 3 revealed that mainly

the entropy of activation controls the reaction rates.

Acknowledgement

Sincere thanks are due to CSIR, New Delhi for financial support.

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